

Aluminium-Modified Biochar-Clay Composite for the Treatment of Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)

E. A Nyebe*, M. Hadi Mosleh*, P. Mandal* and M. Sedighi*

* School of Engineering, The University of Manchester, Manchester M13 9PL, UK
(E-mail: esther.nyebe@manchester.ac.uk; mojgan.hadimosleh@manchester.ac.uk;
majid.sedighi@manchester.ac.uk; partha.mandal@manchester.ac.uk)

Abstract

Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) is among the emerging contaminants of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), known as ‘forever chemicals’, which pose significant environmental and health risks. Developing eco-friendly materials for the treatment of PFOA in wastewater remains a significant challenge. This paper introduces a sustainable and novel biochar-clay composite for the PFOA control in water/wastewater. We have developed the composite by incorporating kaolinite into hardwood biochar (HWB) and activating that with aluminium ions (Al^{3+}) to enhance the adsorption efficiency. The properties of composites were characterised using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive x-ray fluorescence (EDXRF) and their PFOA adsorption capacities were evaluated through batch equilibrium contact-time tests. The results indicate that the Al^{3+} -modified composite ($\text{Al}^{3+}\text{HWB-K}$) exhibits a higher adsorption capacity ($\sim 11 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) compared to HWB ($\sim 7 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) and HWB-K ($\sim 9 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$). The $\text{Al}^{3+}\text{HWB-K}$ composite achieved over 90% removal efficiency. The enhanced performance of $\text{Al}^{3+}\text{HWB-K}$ is attributed to the increased availability of active sites and improved electrostatic interactions introduced by the Al^{3+} ions. The new composite proposed here demonstrates extensive potential as an eco-technological solution for efficient and sustainable PFOA removal from wastewater.

Keywords

Adsorption, Biochar, Kaolinite, PFAS, PFOA, Wastewater treatment

INTRODUCTION

Per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a large group of anthropogenic chemicals characterised by high thermal stability and strong carbon-fluorine bonds, making them valuable in various commercial, industrial, and domestic applications (Hang et al., 2015, Lang et al., 2017). Widespread utilisation and improper disposal of PFAS substances have resulted in environmental contamination, posing significant risks to human health, including hepatotoxicity, immunotoxicity, and neurotoxicity as emerging contaminants of concern (Wu et al., 2022). Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) is one of the prevalent PFAS detected in the environment despite its production discontinuation in the early 2000s and is classified as a persistent organic pollutant (POP) due to its prolonged environmental persistence (Fenton et al., 2021). The molecular structure of PFOA consists of an eight-carbon fully fluorinated hydrophobic tail and a carboxylic functional group head, contributing to its exceptional resistance to bio-environmental degradation (Wu et al., 2022). Wastewater effluent constitutes one of the major sources of environmental PFOA contamination, with concentrations reaching $150 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ potentially posing substantial risks, especially in scenarios involving direct or indirect potable water reuse of wastewater. Consequently, the development and implementation of effective strategies for mitigating PFAS contamination in wastewater systems are crucial for environmental protection and public health.

PFOA treatment by adsorption is an affordable, sustainable, and environmentally friendly approach, whereas alternative treatment methods are energy-intensive and require specific operational conditions (Lath et al., 2018, Hang et al., 2015). Traditional adsorbents, such as granular activated carbon (GAC) (Sukeesan et al., 2023), polymers, green sorption media (GSM) composed of sand (91%), clay (4%), and iron oxide (5%) (Ordonez et al., 2022), and activated carbon fibre (ACF) (Wang et al., 2015), have been used to control PFOA. However, these materials often exhibit slow adsorption rates, potential re-contamination from their chemical composition, and limited efficacy when used individually. Therefore, there is a need to develop novel adsorbents with enhanced adsorption capacity, eco-friendliness, and sustainability.

Kaolinite, an abundant clay mineral with high ion exchange capacity and modifiable functional groups, demonstrates potential as an eco-friendly adsorbent. Nonetheless, their fine particle size poses difficulties in dispersion and recovery during wastewater treatment processes (Wang et al., 2019). Biochar, a carbonaceous material derived from agricultural residues or biomass waste, offers renewable and functional group-rich properties, making it potentially suitable for pollution control applications (Liu et al., 2024). In this study, a novel biochar-clay composite is introduced that was synthesised by loading hardwood biochar (HWB) with kaolinite clay minerals and activating it with Al^{3+} . The properties of the HWB composite and PFOA adsorption capacity were assessed through characterisation and equilibrium contact time tests.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals used are PFOA (97%), LC-MS grade acetonitrile, and aluminium chloride hexahydrate ($\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 99%), obtained from Sigma Aldrich. Materials for synthesising the composite included hardwood biochar (pyrolytic temperature 500 °C, Oxford Charcoal Company, UK) and kaolinite clay (Sigma Aldrich). Both materials were washed with deionised (DI) water (18 $\text{M}\Omega \cdot \text{cm}$), oven-dried for 24 hours, and stored in sealed containers, prior to the application. The composite of hardwood biochar and kaolinite clay was synthesised using post-pyrolysis and slurry methods (Lin et al., 2023). The mixture was stirred for 24 hours, filtered, and oven-dried to produce HWB-K. For aluminium ions modification, kaolinite was treated with 0.4 mM $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, followed by a gradual addition of HWB, and continuous stirring for 24 h at room temperature. The aluminium-modified composite was filtered, washed, and dried at 105 °C to yield Al^{3+} HWB-K. The study utilised pristine HWB, HWB-K, and Al^{3+} HWB-K for adsorption experiments. The surface morphology of HWB, kaolinite and composites were analysed using SEM (FEI Quanta 250FEG-SEM, at 10 kV) and elemental composition was determined using EDXRF (Malvern PANalytical Mini Pal).

A series of batch adsorption experiments were conducted utilising 500 mg of the adsorbents in 20 mL of 200 ng/mL PFOA solution. Samples were collected at various time intervals, filtered through 0.22 μm syringe filters, and aliquots were examined by ultra-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS). The amount of PFOA adsorbed (Q_e/Q_t) and removal efficiency were calculated as previously described (Wu et al., 2022)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterisation of Adsorbent

The SEM analysis (**Figure 1a**) revealed the honeycomb structure of HWB with a smooth surface and irregularly sized, wide-open pores, whereas kaolinite clay exhibited plate-like layered sheets, which are characteristic of silicate minerals. **Figure 1b** illustrates the HWB-K composite with kaolinite layered sheets located on the surface of the HWB, partially occupying its honeycomb pores, a feature more prominently visible at 5 μm magnification. Notably, for the Al^{3+} HWB-K image, the kaolinite clay particles were more dispersed, fragmented, and needle-like, with a rougher surface particle evidenced by bright, crystalline particles adhering to the HWB surface and pores. This feature is absent in HWB-K because of the presence of Al^{3+} ions in the kaolinite clay and HWB, thereby enhancing the composite accessibility for the adsorption potential for PFOA molecules. The elemental analysis (**Figure 1c**) confirmed the successful ion exchange and element binding on the HWB-K and Al^{3+} HWB-K composites. The elemental oxides were SiO_2 (42.1% and 50.1%), Al_2O_3 (24.1% and 30.8%), and CaO (11.9% and 16.7%, respectively). The incorporation of 20% (w/w) kaolinite clay (SiO_2 : 58%, Al_2O_3 : 10.3%) into HWB (CaO: 68%, Al_2O_3 : 0%) increased the elemental content of the composites.

Figure 1. (a/b) SEM images; and (c) EDXRF composition of HWB, HWB-K, and Al³⁺HWB-K.

Adsorption performance

The results of batch adsorption tests on HWB, HWB-K, and Al³⁺HWB-K are presented in **Figure 2a**. The time required to achieve adsorption equilibrium was attained at 7 h for HWB and Al³⁺HWB-K, whereas for HWB-K, equilibrium was reached after 24 h. The adsorption process exhibited a two-step behaviour: an initial rapid uptake was observed within 30 min, as evidenced by the adsorption capacity value, followed by a slower phase until equilibrium was achieved. Furthermore, the adsorption capacities increased in the order: Al³⁺HWB-K (11,023 ng g⁻¹) > HWB-K (9,412 ng g⁻¹) > HWB (7,152 ng g⁻¹). Additionally, a high removal efficiency of Al³⁺HWB-K > 90% was observed. The removal efficiencies for HWB-K and HWB were approximately 70%, and 53%, respectively. The enhanced sorption observed with Al³⁺HWB-K can be attributed to the incorporation of Al³⁺ ions into the HWB-K composite, which increased the PFOA adsorption by 22%.

The removal efficiency of Al³⁺HWB-K exceeded that of other adsorbents (**Figure 2b**), highlighting the significance of incorporating Al³⁺ ions onto HWB-K relative to the composite with Al³⁺ ions. The enhanced performance is attributed to the Al³⁺ ions, which improved the structural properties and surface adsorption capacity of HWB-K by creating more active sites and acting as a bridge that interact with PFOA molecules, thereby increasing removal efficiency. This observation highlights the advantage of adding cationic elements to HWB-K, introducing additional active sites to enhance adsorbate-adsorbent interactions through electrostatic interaction mechanisms.

Figure 2. (a) Adsorption capacity of PFOA by HWB, HWB-K, and Al³⁺HWB-K (b) Removal efficiency of different adsorbents.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a biochar-clay composite was successfully synthesised by combining hardwood biochar (HWB) with kaolinite and activating that with Al³⁺ ions. Al³⁺HWB-K perform as an efficient, eco-friendly adsorbent for PFOA control in wastewater treatment. The composite achieved a high adsorption capacity of 11,023 ng g⁻¹ and over 90% removal efficiency, much higher than that of HWB, and HWB-K. The enhancement is attributed to Al³⁺ ions, which improved surface properties, introduced additional active sites, and facilitated electrostatic interactions with PFOA molecules. By combining renewable biochar and abundant kaolinite clay, this composite can be an effective solution for some of the key challenges in wastewater engineering, including the need for sustainable, cost-effective, and high-performance adsorbents. Its scalability and environmental compatibility position it as a promising material for PFAS mitigation, contributing to cleaner water systems and eco-technological advancements.

REFERENCES

- Fenton, S. E., Dewitt, C., Ng, & Roberts, S. M. 2021. Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substance Toxicity and Human Health Review: Current State of Knowledge and Strategies for Future Research. *Environ Toxicol Chem*.
- Hang, X., Chen, X., Luo, J., Cao, W. & Wan, Y. 2015. Removal and recovery of perfluorooctanoate from wastewater by nanofiltration. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 145, 120-129.
- Lang, J. R., Allred, B. M., Field, J. A., Levis, J. W. & Barlaz, M. A. 2017. National Estimate of Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substance (PFAS) Release to U.S. Municipal Landfill Leachate. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 51.
- Lath, S., Navarro, D., Losic, D., Kumar, A. & Mclaughlin, M. 2018. Sorptive remediation of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) using mixed mineral and graphene/carbon-based materials. *Environmental Chemistry*, 15.
- Liu, Z.-Z., Pan, C.-G., Peng, F.-J., Hu, J.-J., Tan, H.-M., Zhu, R.-G., Zhou, C.-Y., Liang, H. & Yu, K. 2024. Rapid adsorptive removal of emerging and legacy per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) from water using zinc chloride-modified litchi seed-derived biochar. *Bioresource Technology*, 408, 131157.
- Ordenez, D., Valencia, A., Sadmani, A. H. M. A. & Chang, N.-B. 2022. Green sorption media for the removal of perfluorooctanesulfonic acid and perfluorooctanoic acid from water. *Science of The Total Environment*, 819.
- Sukeesan, S., Boontanon, N., Fujii, S. & Boontanon, S. K. 2023. Evaluation of the adsorption behavior of mixed perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances onto granular activated carbon. *Remediation Journal*, 33, 297.
- Wang, X., Gu, Y., Tan, X., Liu, Y., Hu, X., Cai, X., Xu, W., Zhang, C. & Liu, S. 2019. Functionalized Biochar/Clay Composites for Reducing the Bioavailable Fraction of Arsenic. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*.
- Wang, Y., Niu, J., Li, Y., Zheng, T., Xu, Y. & Liu, Y. 2015. Performance and mechanisms for removal of perfluorooctanoate (PFOA) from aqueous solution by activated carbon fiber. *RSC Advances*, 5, 86927..
- Wu, Y., Qi, L. & Chen, G. 2022. A mechanical investigation of perfluorooctane acid adsorption by engineered biochar. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 340, 130742.